

A Study of Women Entrepreneurs in Coimbatore District to Explore the Harmony Between Work and Life Engagement

Dr R Sivaramakrishnan, Assistant Professor,
PG & Research Department of International Business,
Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore

ORCID : [0009-0001-4275-7947](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4275-7947)

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The study seeks to examine the experiences of 120 female entrepreneurs through a survey, with the objective of gaining insights into their strategies for achieving equilibrium between their home responsibilities and business pursuits." Consequently, Women today must fulfill a variety of responsibilities at all ages of their existence. Some of the increasingly major professions chosen by women is being an entrepreneur who handles commercial operations in addition to family duties. Successfully combining both one's personal and professional lives is what is meant by "having a harmonious work-life balance." Hence, the primary intent of the current research is to determine how the work-life harmony of Coimbatore District's female entrepreneurs. The difficulty of balancing work and family obligations affects working women executives. The problem of role conflict is brought on by growing family duties and possible positions.

KEYWORDS: *Women entrepreneurs, navigating role conflicts, professional and personal lives*

Introduction

Self-employment has become essential for individuals seeking to arrange their time in accordance with their personal and professional needs. Women, in particular, experience unique emotional motivations influenced by both push and pull factors. Pull factors include a sense of self-awareness, feelings of self-worth, autonomy, the opportunity to be one's own boss, the ability to establish one's own rules and guidelines, and increased financial security. Push factors encompass dissatisfaction with their current professions, financial challenges within the family, and the demands of raising and nurturing children.

The surge in female-owned businesses has gained momentum due to the increasing globalization, as well as the effects of progressive social, economic, and cultural trends, along with advancements in technology and media. Women entrepreneurs have earned recognition for their significant contributions to global economic growth and vitality. They achieve this by generating innovative ideas, identifying opportunities in their immediate surroundings, securing resources, and seizing those opportunities.

In traditionally patriarchal societies like India, men have historically been encouraged to seek employment or engage in business. However, in recent times, there has been a shift, with women also being encouraged to pursue these paths. The role of women in the workforce has undergone a substantial transformation in the era of globalization. Women are increasingly developing entrepreneurial ideas, but as workplace responsibilities expand, finding a balance between personal and professional commitments becomes more challenging

Review of Literature

Srinivasa Rao (2006) emphasized the crucial significance of achieving a work-life balance, as it impacts the efficiency of both employees and supervisors. Arunpandian (2001) presented research findings indicating that women view entrepreneurship as a means to enhance their professional, financial, and personal lives, albeit with potential negative implications for their family roles. These women often encountered conflicts between their entrepreneurial responsibilities and their roles as homemakers, parents, and spouses.

Despite these challenges, the allure of exciting ideas and technological breakthroughs has driven many women to pursue both their household responsibilities and careers. The imbalance experienced by women in juggling work and family life is a byproduct of prevailing social and economic conditions, emphasizing the need for respectful and open-minded treatment (Albandu 1996).

Jayashankar (2007) pointed out that factors such as freedom and adaptability in work schedules play a pivotal role in how effectively female entrepreneurs integrate their personal and professional lives. Additionally, John (2008) explored freelance business ownership as a potential solution to the role conflicts experienced by women managing both work and family obligations concurrently.

In further research conducted by Thamarai Selvi. (2021), the relationship between work and personal life among women in business was investigated. The study revealed that the current competitive business environment has intensified operational demands and exacerbated conflicts between the two domains. According to their report, female entrepreneurs must acquire a comprehensive understanding and relevant skills to effectively manage stress and run their enterprises successfully.

Statement of the Problem

Women's professional aspirations often face impediments due to prevailing social norms, as they are expected to fulfill multiple and often conflicting roles in society. Simultaneously juggling household and entrepreneurial responsibilities leads to conflicts between work and family life. It is crucial for their professional growth and economic sustainability that they establish a harmonious equilibrium

between their work and home lives. Several studies have identified conflicts and imbalances in managing work and life as factors contributing to poor well-being and reduced satisfaction.

The primary objective of this present study is to identify the competing demands of home and entrepreneurship roles and assess their significance in maintaining a healthy work-life balance.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the socioeconomic characteristics of women business owners in Coimbatore District
2. To explore how women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore District City balance their work and personal lives.
3. To investigate the variables affecting women entrepreneurs' balance between work and life

Materials and Methods

Information for the current study were gathered from sources that were secondary as well as primary. A well-designed questionnaire was used to collect first-hand information from female business owners. A questionnaire was used to gather information about 120 female business owners in Coimbatore District and examine their work-life balance.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Reliability Test

The Cronbach's Alpha test has been used to assess the validity of the questions. As there were 41 total elements, we received a Cronbach's Alpha value of .90, which is significant.

Cronbach's alpha value is 0.933.

Age of the Respondents

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
less than 25 years	12	12
26 to 35 years	66	56
36 to 45 years	28	28
46 to 55 years	14	4
TOTAL		100%

Marital Status of the Respondent

STATUS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
married	90	85
unmarried	30	15

Educational Qualifications

QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
UG	68	68
PG	25	18
SCHOOL LEVEL	27	14

RESPONSIBILITY & ROLE	SA	A	N	DA	SD A	TOTA L
less time to attend the Personal Commitment.	47	23	0	17	13	120
The time allocated for spending with your family is inadequate.	76	14	2	4	4	120
Your limited availability for your children's studies delays their academic progress.	24	14	3	45	14	120
You struggle to sustain stable relationships with both family and friends.	12	13	3	64	8	120
You sacrifice your hobbies and leisure activities.	34	14	13	36	3	120

7. LEVEL OF SATISFACTION WITH WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS' PROVISIONS FOR CHILDCARE

PARTICULARS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Satisfied	36	36
Not Satisfied	84	84

Factors Distressing Women Entrepreneurs

FACTORS	MEAN VALUE
Lack of training	4.02
Unsupportive family	4.22
Lack of networking	4.12
Passion	4.00
Lack of fund support	4.32

This table presents the mean values of different factors affecting a certain situation. Lack of Training (Mean Value: 4.02) - On average, respondents perceive that a lack of training is a significant factor influencing the situation. This suggests that respondents generally feel that inadequate training plays a role in the situation's challenges. Unsupportive Family (Mean Value: 4.22) - The mean value for unsupportive family indicates that, on average, respondents consider this factor to be relatively influential. It suggests that respondents believe that lack of support from their families is a notable challenge in the situation. Lack of Networking (Mean Value: 4.12) - Respondents, on average, rate the lack of networking as a significant factor, albeit slightly lower than the unsupportive family factor. This suggests that respondents perceive networking challenges as a noteworthy aspect of the situation. Passion (Mean Value: 4.00) - Passion has a mean value of 4.00, indicating that, on average, respondents consider it a moderately important factor. It suggests that respondents view passion as a factor that contributes to the situation but not as influential as some other factors. Lack of Fund Support (Mean Value: 4.32) - The highest mean value in this list, 4.32, indicates that respondents see a lack of fund support as the most influential factor in the situation. This suggests that respondents believe that insufficient financial support is a significant challenge that needs to be addressed.

These mean values provide an overview of how respondents perceive the importance of these factors in the context of the situation being studied. Higher mean values indicate greater perceived significance.

Findings of the Study

The survey revealed several key challenges faced by female business owners in Coimbatore District regarding work-life balance:

Long Working Hours: The primary concern among female business owners is the long working hours they invest in their businesses. Many respondents reported that they often find themselves working extended hours, which can have adverse effects on their personal lives.

Limited Family Time: Balancing work and family time emerged as a significant issue. Female entrepreneurs expressed concerns about spending less time with their immediate families, including spouses and children. The demands of their businesses often take precedence over family commitments.

Reduced Time for Unique Relatives: Respondents noted that they have less time to devote to extended family members and unique relatives due to their business obligations. This can result in strained relationships and feelings of guilt.

Reluctance to Participate in Social Events: Female business owners sometimes feel reluctant to participate in social events and gatherings due to their demanding work schedules. This can lead to social isolation and a lack of participation in their communities.

Sacrificing Family Obligations: Some respondents indicated that they felt compelled to sacrifice family obligations in pursuit of their business success. This may involve missing important family events or not being available during family emergencies.

Discussion & Suggestion:

The challenges identified among female business owners in Coimbatore District are indicative of the broader issues faced by women entrepreneurs globally. Achieving a satisfactory work-life balance is often elusive due to the demands of entrepreneurship. Long working hours, the pressure to succeed, and the need to compete in the business landscape can strain personal relationships and lead to burnout.

Conclusion:

The findings of this report highlight the pressing need to address work-life balance issues faced by female business owners in Coimbatore District. Policy interventions, support systems, and awareness campaigns can play a crucial role in helping these entrepreneurs achieve a more harmonious balance between their professional and personal lives. By addressing these challenges, we can empower female entrepreneurs to thrive in both their businesses and personal relationships, fostering overall well-being and success.

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